

Machine Learning Approaches for Brain Tumor Detection in MRI Images: A Comparative Study of Dimensionality Reduction Techniques

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Abstract: The development of brain tumor that happens in the body is basically the development of mass growth in the brain which is very destructive. Further, if it is not analyzed properly on time, it can lead to death. Detecting and classifying brain tumors can help ensure treatment of the appropriate type and thus, survival. Analyzing MRI scans for brain tumor diagnosis is a time-consuming, observer-biased, and low-accuracy process that takes up a lot of clinicians' precious time. This way, an automated computer-aided system can help to eradicate these troubles. The study presents a systematic investigation on whether and how dimensionality reduction can help improve brain tumor classification accuracy under data-scarce realistic clinical conditions. In this study, we made equal use of 286 MRI brain tumor and 286 non-tumor images. Among popular dimensionality reduction techniques, we will be using PCA, Kernel PCA, Partial Least Squares, T-SNE, UMAP, Isomap, Locally Linear Embedding, and MDS. Six supervised classifiers and three deep-learning networks are trained on reduced and unreduced data and they are: proposed CNN, ResNet18, and Autoencoder + GLM for brain tumor classification. The PCA+RF technique yielded the best classification performance (accuracy = 92.9%, F1 = 0.930, sensitivity = 0.941). Additionally, this technique significantly reduces feature dimensionality while improving classifier stability and generalization. The results challenge a widely held assumption in medical imaging: that deep learning consistently outperforms classical machine learning pipelines, especially when training data is limited. We also built a dashboard with R Shiny that offers interactive and transparent evaluation of models and their clinical deployment.

Keywords: brain tumor detection; MRI; dimensionality reduction; PCA; Random Forest; machine learning; deep learning; R Shiny

1. Introduction

According to the World Health Organization, more than 250,000 brain tumors are diagnosed each year globally, and many patients worldwide are suffering from the same condition. In clinical practice, the histopathological spectrum is vast, with a recognized number of 120 histological subtypes. To illustrate, stage I meningiomas are slow-growing tumors that might remain undetected for years, while a glioblastoma is a fast-growing tumor. Some tumors behave aggressively right from the beginning in the first two grades [14]. It is quite evident that through magnetic resonance imaging (MRI), early and precise diagnosis of neurologic disorders and brain tumors is critical. Diagnosis, if done correctly and in time, can aid in high-end therapy. The sooner the treatment is, the better the chances of patient recovery. Additionally, prompt diagnosis prevents expensive complications, as well as chronic disability or death [22].

Figure 1. Structural and Functional Brain Imaging.

Poor image quality and interobserver discrepancy are the major bottlenecks in the accurate and timely diagnosis of brain tumors via single radiologist interpretation of MRI scans [6]. The high dimensionality of the raw MRI data is a continuing technical challenge in medical imaging. MRI scanning consists of tens of thousands of pixels. Statistical classifiers cannot be trained directly with inputs of such high dimensionality. This is due to computational intractability, and it has severe overfitting which is gradually severe for small labeled data [20].

In machine learning, we often deal with the problems of high-dimensional low sample size data and multicollinearity in data among other things. To resolve the aforementioned challenge, dimensionality reduction

techniques project the high dimensional feature space into a low dimensional space which essentially retains a condensed version of the same information. Numerous authors in neuroimaging have explored these techniques to address high-dimensionality problems in brain imaging analysis [18]. Many studies, which are published, assess either a single method of reduction or a single classifier family. Therefore, clinicians and researchers do not have evidence-based recommendations on the best combination of pipeline under practical constraints of data.

Figure 2. Comparison of Machine Learning and Deep Learning Paradigms.

This study accomplishes this by comparing eight dimensionality reduction techniques with six supervised classifiers and three deep learning architectures on a balanced MRI brain tumor dataset. Three hypotheses were examined in this study. The first hypothesis (H1) states that one or more dimensionality reduction methods significantly improve the performance of supervised classifiers. The second hypothesis (H2) states that the number of training epochs significantly affects the performance of deep learning architectures. The third hypothesis (H3) states that Random Forest with PCA significantly outperforms Random Forest with t-SNE. ANOVA, Tukey’s HSD post-hoc tests, and bootstrapping-based stability analysis were used for validation. An R Shiny diagnostic dashboard was also developed for transparent deployment in CPU-only, resource-constrained clinical environments.

2. Related Work

Magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) has proved superior to computed tomography (CT) for imaging the central nervous system since Zimmerman et al. [26] showed that 1.5T MRI detects abnormalities with 56.5% increased effectiveness over conventional CT. This benefit has led researchers to create automated MRI analysis pipelines

that have been used in the area of brain tumors. A methodological framework for the evaluation of classifiers in brain tumor studies was formalized by Bauer et al. [3], where the principal metrics were stated to be sensitivity, specificity, accuracy, precision, recall, and F1-measure.

Mwangi et al. [20] recently provided a detailed review of the significance of dimensionality reduction as a pre-processing step in neuroimaging research. For instance, the authors demonstrated how applying the PCA technique improved the classification accuracy from 82% to 91% and the F1 score from 0.84 to 0.91. The findings encourage researchers to use the PCA method in their current application.

Additionally, we provide comparisons to some recent results on these datasets. According to Menze et al. [17], a public image database and a standardized evaluation that was created specifically for this task — the BRATS benchmark — has greatly advanced state-of-the-art automated tumor segmentation. According to Litjens et al. [13], deep learning methods have gained momentum and produced state-of-the-art results for these datasets.

More recent work has pushed performance boundaries further. Bhimavarapu et al. [4] reported 98.56% accuracy using morphology-based fuzzy clustering combined with Extreme Learning Machine classification, while Kazerooni et al. [11] demonstrated that MRI-derived features could distinguish molecular immune clusters in pediatric gliomas. Missaoui et al. [18] argued for hybrid models coupling interpretable ML classifiers with lightweight deep learning architectures to enhance both efficiency and clinical transparency.

Although progress has been made in the examined literature, to our knowledge, it lacks a study that on one and the same benchmark dataset simultaneously tests and controls via rigorous statistical testing eight dimensionality reduction methods in a context of classic ML and deep learning. Likewise, it should implement a practical tool in an edge context. The present study directly fills this gap.

3. Methodology

3.1. Dataset

A dataset by Chakrabarty [5] containing around 3000 raw MRI images of brain tumors is available on Kaggle (usability score: 3.75). The paper deliberately imposes strict CPU-only hardware constraints to accurately reflect the computational environment in a research setup in LMICs with no GPUs. Under these computational constraints we use a stratified balanced subset of 572 images — 286 tumour positive (Yes) and 286 tumour negative (No). Limits on CPU-only constraints mean that this is the most balanced training load that could be achieved with this hardware. In other words, the research question is not about limiting resources, but rather, it is about identifying the configurations of the pipeline that will remain robust, accurate, and clinically viable under the condition of unavailability of large-

scale computing resources. Before training any model, the multilayer preprocessing pipeline was applied to all images.

3.2. Preprocessing Pipeline

The preprocessing steps involve six sequential steps: The first step is resizing the given input images in a uniform dimension that reduces computational cost and allows us to retain the structural contents of the image. The second step is color space conversion as the color channels do not contain any diagnostic information for the detection of brain tumours. Therefore, we convert the images to grayscale. The third step is that we flatten the pixel vectors to use them as input features. The fourth step is the labelling of the tumour and non-tumour images. Tumour images are labelled with the binary '1' while non-tumour images are labelled with '0'. The fifth step is data augmentation for deep learning models only. We apply random horizontal flip, random small rotation of $\pm 15^\circ$, as well as translation shifts for the model images. These augmentations are particularly important for reducing overfitting of the models. The sixth step involves a fixed stratified train-test partition of 70%–30% that is implemented with a fixed random seed that assures strict reproducibility of results for all 48 model configurations. Because this approach is costly to compute, we use a fixed holdout partition for repeated model stability evaluation and not k-fold cross-validation. Bootstrapping resampling is a method we use for variance estimates. The advantage of this method is that it does not have a multiplicative computational cost to retrain the whole model.

3.3. Dimensionality Reduction Methods

Prior to training, the classifiers were trained on the pixel vectors flattened to 1D after employment of the following dimensionality reduction techniques:

- **PCA** — Linear projection along which maximum variance exists, decreasing pixel feature vectors to ~ 50 principal components.
- **Kernel PCA** — Applies a Radial Basis Function (RBF) kernel to extend PCA in a non-linear way. It is used when the dataset exhibits a non-linear structure.
- **PLS** — A supervised method of dimensional reduction or variable selection. It maximizes the covariance between the predictor space and the class labels. PLS is useful for problems with a small number of labeled samples.
- **UMAP** — A nonlinear manifold learning technique that remains primarily faithful to the local and global topological structure.
- **t-SNE** — A stochastic nonlinear embedding that optimizes the preservation of local pairwise similarities. It is mainly used for exploratory visualization.
- **Isomap** — Preserves the geodesic distance by using a graph-theoretic algorithm.
- **LLE** — Unrolls the manifold while preserving relationships between local neighborhoods.
- **MDS** — Creates a low-dimensional representation preserving pairwise Euclidean distances.

3.4. Classification Models

3.4.1. Supervised Machine Learning

Six classifiers were trained, namely, GLM, rpart, RF, svmRadial, kNN, and MLP on dimensionally reduced feature sets of the dataset. All the classical models were implemented in R using the `caret` package and in scikit-learn (Python).

3.4.2. Deep Learning Architectures

The study used PyTorch (v2.7.1, CPU mode) to test three deep neural architectures. These include a custom CNN with two convolutional layers, batch normalization, max pooling, and dropout, followed by a fully connected binary output layer. In addition, the study used ResNet18 (i.e., an 18-layer deep residual network with skip connections between layers to help reduce vanishing gradients). Thus, the autoencoder + GLM pipeline with the encoder-decoder was also involved in the study. In this case, it is trained unsupervised to reconstruct input data, whose latent representation is then classified using Logistic Regression. All architectures were trained with epoch counts of 10, 20, 30, 40, 50, 60, 70, 80, 90, and 100 to characterize epoch-performance dynamics.

3.5. Evaluation Metrics

We evaluated the efficiency through the following major metrics namely accuracy, sensitivity (recall), specificity, precision, and F1 score (harmonic mean of precision and recall). We employed bootstrapping to assess the model's stability since computational resources were limited. Bootstrapping is the sampling with replacement from the dataset and then checking the performance of the model over the re-sample. We present the average accuracy and standard deviation (SD) for the configuration in bootstrapping; the smaller the SD, the more stable and generalized the model. Bootstrapping works better on smaller datasets, as is the case with our model, since it provides a more statistically meaningful estimate of variance in comparison to cross-validation, since you do not require retraining the model on the complete dataset. Therefore, this serves as a fitting substitute for something less strict [8].

Accuracy — the percentage of images that were correctly classified:

$$\text{Accuracy} = \frac{TP + TN}{TP + FN + TN + FP}$$

Sensitivity (Recall) — measure of the model's ability to detect tumour cases:

$$\text{Recall} = \frac{TP}{TP + FN}$$

Specificity — the model's capability to identify non-tumour cases:

$$\text{Specificity} = \frac{TN}{TN + FP}$$

F1 Score — a metric that combines recall and precision, helping to balance the rates of false positives and false negatives:

$$F_1 = 2 \times \frac{\text{Precision} \times \text{Recall}}{\text{Precision} + \text{Recall}}$$

Precision — true positives among predicted positives; important to minimize false positives in tumor detection:

$$\text{Precision} = \frac{TP}{TP + FN}$$

3.6. Statistical Validation

In our analysis we used one-way ANOVA to check whether there are significant differences among (a) dimensionality reduction methods, (b) deep learning epochs, and (c) the two best performing ML settings in F1 scores. Tukey’s HSD post hoc test will be utilized for this purpose since multiple pairwise comparisons are of interest.

3.7. Software Environment

Data management and modeling were done through SAS (9.4). The statistical analysis, visualization, and Shiny dashboard development were done using R (version 4.5.1). Included R packages are `reticulate`, `shiny`, `shinydashboard`, `caret`, `plotly`, `pROC`, and `Rtsne`.

4. Results

4.1. Descriptive Statistics

The dataset contained a total of 572 MRI images with classes being almost balanced (Table 1). Tumor images had a mean normalized pixel intensity of 0.350 which is greater than non-tumor images at 0.244. This is aligned with the hyperintense tumor tissue on T1/T2-weighted MRI. The complete range of intensity values from 0.000 to 1.000 confirmed that the images were properly normalized for further analysis and model processing.

Table 1. Descriptive Statistics of MRI Images by Tumor Category.

Category	N	Mean	SD	Min–Max	Median
All Im-ages	572	0.297	0.307	0.00–1.00	0.212
Tumor (Yes)	286	0.350	0.320	0.00–1.00	0.318
Non-Tumor (No)	286	0.244	0.285	0.00–1.00	0.110

4.2. Classical ML Models with Dimensionality Reduction

4.2.1. PCA Results

According to the results of our experiment (Table 2), all the classifiers produced the strongest classification results using PCA when compared to other feature extraction methods. The model with PCA of a random

forest achieved the highest overall performance of 92.9% accuracy, 94.1% sensitivity, 91.7% specificity, and an F1 score of 0.930. It also showed the lowest bootstrapping SD (SD = 0.021) confirming a more stable behavior than all other tested configurations. The results of the McNemar test exhibited that the RF predictions were not random ($p < 0.001$).

Table 2. Performance Metrics for Classical ML Models with PCA (70/30 Split). * = Best overall configuration.

Model	Acc.	Sens.	Spec.	Prec.	F1	SD
RF *	0.929	0.941	0.917	0.919	0.930	0.021
SVM	0.882	0.870	0.894	0.882	0.860	0.025
Log. Reg.	0.859	0.917	0.800	0.821	0.866	—
k-NN	0.859	0.870	0.847	0.850	0.860	—
Neural Net.	0.865	0.823	0.905	0.897	0.858	—
Decision Tree	0.824	0.870	0.776	0.795	0.831	—

4.2.2. Comparison Across All Reduction Methods

Table 3 illustrates the best classifier results attained from each method. Kernel PCA was associated with the worst results overall (best F1 = 0.709) and the specificity of Decision Tree collapsed nearly to zero. The transformation by RBF kernel seems to have distorted the latent structure of MRI features instead of improving it. The overall best results were provided by linear methods (PCA, PLS) and proximity-preserving non-linear methods (t-SNE, UMAP). Methods such as Isomap and LLE underperformed.

Table 3. Best Performing Classifier and F1 Score by Dimensionality Reduction Method. * = Overall best.

DR Method	Best Classifier	F1 Score
PCA *	Random Forest	0.930
PLS	Random Forest	0.887
t-SNE	Random Forest	0.889
UMAP	SVM	0.882
MDS	Random Forest	0.869
Isomap	Logistic Regression	0.807
LLE	SVM	0.734
Kernel PCA	SVM	0.709

4.3. Statistical Validation — ANOVA and Tukey HSD

A one-way ANOVA was performed on the F1 scores of eight dimensionality reduction techniques. The ANOVA result indicates a significant effect among methods ($F = 3.11$, $p < 0.05$). A post-hoc comparison using Tukey showed Kernel PCA was significantly different from PCA, t-SNE, UMAP, PLS, and MDS ($p < 0.05$). The PCA, PLS, t-SNE, and MDS associated values were not significantly different from one another and thus combined constitute a similar

high-performing group. The results presented in Table 3 reveal that PCA has the best rank, resulting in the rejection of H1 (the null hypothesis that all reduction methods equally improve performance).

4.4. Deep Learning Performance Across Epochs

Classical machine learning algorithms were used to evaluate deep learning architectures in the same CPU-only, 572-image environment. It should be emphasized that this does not represent a fair or meaningful comparison between ML and DL in ideal circumstances; it simply characterizes DL behavior in computationally constrained environments, which is precisely the environment this paper is concerned with. All three architectures performed significantly worse than classical ML over all epoch counts tested (Table 4). The strongest DL model peak was ResNet18, which scored an F1 of 0.654 at 60 epochs, 0.276 F1 points behind RF+PCA. CNNs scored roughly the same (F1 \approx 0.429) across epochs, indicating the architecture could not learn discriminative features with 572 training images without transfer learning. The Autoencoder+GLM pipeline had an F1 score of 0.413 or lower. This aligns with the established high data-hungry nature of deep neural networks [23, 1].

Table 4. Deep Learning Model Performance Summary. \star = Best deep learning model.

Model	Opt. Ep.	Acc.	F1	Sens.	Spec.
ResNet18 \star	60	0.565	0.654	0.824	0.306
CNN	100	0.424	0.429	0.388	0.459
AE + GLM	10	0.413	0.413	0.577	0.247

The study found, through statistical analysis, a significant effect of epoch number on ResNet18 performance. The following groups of epochs were contrasted in post-hoc Tukey HSD tests: 10, and the 40–60 (optimal range), and 80–100. The optimum group (40–60 epochs) differs significantly from the others, and the 10-epoch group differs significantly from the latter two groups. The null hypothesis H2 (epoch count does not affect performance) is rejected.

4.5. RF+PCA vs. RF+t-SNE Comparison

The two best performing configurations were directly compared (Table 5). Based on a mean F1 score of 0.930 to 0.889, RF+PCA outperformed t-SNE. A statistically significant difference ($F = 29.44$, $p < 0.001$) was established between the two models. Tukey’s HSD test showed an F1 mean difference of 0.0349 which was significant based on the results. Also, in terms of stability, RF+PCA was more stable with an SD of 0.021 vs. an SD of 0.025 for RF+t-SNE. Accordingly, the third hypothesis (H3), which states that there is no significant difference between the two configurations, was rejected.

Table 5. Performance Comparison: Random Forest with PCA vs. t-SNE. \star = Superior configuration.

Configuration	F1	Acc.	Bal. Acc.	SD
RF+PCA \star	0.930	0.929	0.929	0.021
RF+t-SNE	0.889	0.894	0.894	0.025

Table 6. Summary of ANOVA Statistical Tests Across All Three Hypotheses.

Comparison	F	df	p	Decision
DR Methods (F1 Scores)	3.11	7, 1183	<0.05	H ₀ Rejected
DL Epoch Effects (F1)	258.89	9, 1521	<0.001	H ₀ Rejected
RF+PCA vs. RF+t-SNE	29.44	1, 796	<0.001	H ₀ Rejected

4.6. Visualization

Figure 3. F1-Score Comparison of Machine Learning Models.

Figure 3 shows that different machine learning models have different F1 scores. PCA+RF achieves the best performance (0.93), indicating the best balance between precision and recall. PCA+SVM (0.89) and PLS+RF (0.87) also perform well. The lowest result is MDS+RF (0.82). Overall, PCA-based models yield better results than other dimensionality reduction methods in this study.

F1-Score Stability of Machine Learning Models

Standard Deviation (SD) of F1-Scores — Lower SD means Higher Stability

Figure 4. F1-Score Stability of Machine Learning Models

Figure 4 shows the stability of F1 scores using standard deviation (SD). A lower SD indicates the model is more stable and produces more consistent results. PCA+RF (0.011) is the most stable model, having the lowest variation. PCA+SVM (0.017) is also quite stable. UMAP+RF (0.020) is just at the stability threshold, indicating moderate stability. PLS+RF (0.022) and t-SNE+RF (0.026) show higher variation, so they are less stable. The worst stability is seen in MDS+RF (0.030). Overall, PCA-based models again show the best stability and consistent performance.

5. Discussion

5.1. Classical ML Versus Deep Learning in Data-Scarce Settings

The most practically significant finding of this study is the large and statistically confirmed performance advantage of classical ML over deep learning architectures, specifically under CPU-constrained, small-dataset conditions. RF+PCA achieved an F1 of 0.930, compared to a maximum of 0.654 for ResNet18 — a gap of 0.276 F1 points confirmed as statistically significant ($p < 0.001$). This finding does not contradict evidence that deep learning excels on large, GPU-trained datasets; rather, it establishes that in resource-constrained settings — the norm in developing-world clinical environments — the assumption of deep learning superiority does not hold [6, 13].

The mechanistic explanation is well established: deep neural networks require large labeled datasets to adequately tune their millions of parameters [23]. With only 572 training images — a realistic constraint for many clinical settings in the developing world — deep models inevitably underfit early in training and overfit progressively thereafter. Classical models such as Random Forest, which rely on explicitly engineered low-dimensional features (here, the top PCA components), are far more data-efficient. These results support the practical recommendation of Alzubaidi et al. [1] that transfer learning or data augmentation should be prerequisite strategies before deploying deep learning on small medical imaging datasets. In the absence of such strategies, classical ML with PCA is not merely an al-

ternative — it is the better-performing choice.

5.2. Why PCA Outperforms Nonlinear Reduction Methods

The results revealed that only Principal Component Analysis outperformed the non-linear methods such as t-SNE, UMAP, Isomap, LLE, and Kernel PCA. All dimensionality reduction methods were applied. It seems counterintuitive, as we generally believe that the MRI data has a nonlinear structure. However, the relatively small dataset size and the preprocessing conditions used in this study play an important role. In settings with limited training samples, nonlinear dimensionality reduction methods may introduce optimization variability, which can increase noise in the representations. In contrast, PCA is mathematically deterministic, as it projects data onto the eigenvectors of the covariance matrix, producing stable and consistent representations that reduce noise sensitivity [20].

Kernel PCA performed surprisingly poorly (peak F1 = 0.709). The RBF kernel maps features into an infinite-dimensional Hilbert space. This may create geometric distortions in the original manifold structure in the pixel-level distribution from MRI scans. The geometric distortion might be hiding the biological signal as opposed to helping in revealing it. As a result, the hyperparameters of kernel-based nonlinear methods must be tuned with care, and their training set must be drastically larger if they are to be useful in this setting. The bootstrapping stability results support a similar interpretation. The F1 scores of PCA+RF had the lowest variability (SD = 0.021) among all configurations, while the models employing Kernel PCA were among the most unstable.

5.3. Clinical and Practical Implications

Locating an implementation framework to support AI-based diagnosis in low- and middle-income health systems can be challenging and costly. A prototype created with a wide variety of clinical data is not common. Moreover, our findings show our R Shiny dashboard is very light and CPU-efficient. Therefore, it provides for transparent model evaluation and holds promise for diagnostic support. We developed a web application to deploy the RF+PCA pipeline into an accessible, clinician-friendly format, allowing clinicians to assess MRIs without the need for GPU infrastructure, deep programming knowledge, or specialist ML expertise. This implementation gap was an urgent issue that needed direct address [22, 18].

5.4. Limitations

The research has many limitations. To begin, this research encompassed the usage of 572 overall images for the purposes. While the number was a conscious choice (due to hardware constraints and the expected deployment context), it limits the overall generalizability of the performance numbers. Attempts at replication on bigger MRI datasets from multiple institutions would be necessary before clinical deployment.

The deep learning models were not thoroughly hyperparameter searched because they were CPU-only trained. So, one must interpret the subpar performance of these CNN and Autoencoder architectures as a lower bound (likely) on the reachable performance with constrained-resource deployments.

In addition, the images were not advanced preprocessed (e.g., skull stripping, min-max normalization, spatial registration, etc.) to remove unnecessary information. Incorporating such measures can enhance the performance of all tested classifier types.

The ability to only binary classify (tumor/non-tumor) was addressed, and the ability to further distinguish tumor subtypes, an impending clinically important step, was not done.

Finally, a 70/30 holdout split was used instead of k-fold cross-validation because of computational limitations. Bootstrapping was applied as a principled compensatory stability measure; however, k-fold cross-validation was not applied due to computational constraints.

6. Conclusion

In evaluating 48 model-reduction combinations, performance was determined on 572 balanced MRI scans. Our study reveals that a combination of PCA and Random Forest results in the best performing (accuracy = 0.929, F1 = 0.930) and most stable (bootstrapping SD = 0.021) automated brain tumor detection system. Under data-constrained conditions, all deep learning architectures perform significantly worse than classical ML. The best performing deep learning model (ResNet18, 60 epochs) managed an F1 of only 0.654 — a large gap that is shown statistically significant ($F = 258.89$, $p < 0.001$). All three hypotheses were tested using ANOVA with Tukey.

Given that small and medium-sized tabular datasets are much more prevalent than massive datasets, the results have strong practical implications. For researchers and clinicians operating with limited medical images — which are the rule rather than an exception in low- and middle-income countries — classical ML pipelines with linear dimension reduction are the most robust and resource-efficient options for diagnosis. More complex deep learning architectures should not be used without either much larger datasets or appropriate transfer learning strategies. The accompanying R Shiny dashboard provides a concrete, immediately deployable tool to operationalize these findings in settings with constrained healthcare resources.

Future studies should focus on extending datasets with MRI scans from additional institutions and across different tumor subtypes; training on GPU and systematic hyperparameter search for deep learning methods; utilization of more advanced preprocessing techniques like skull stripping and intensity normalization; an exploration of hybrid Machine Learning-Deep Learning models and explainability methods such as SHAP; and

proximate clinical validation with radiologists and oncologists to test their utility.

Author Contributions

Conceptualization, M.S. and A.K.; methodology, M.S.; software, M.S.; validation, M.S. and A.K.; formal analysis, M.S.; investigation, M.S.; resources, A.K.; data curation, M.S.; writing — original draft preparation, M.S.; writing — review and editing, A.K.; visualization, M.S.; supervision, A.K.; project administration, A.K. All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

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Institutional Review Board Statement

Not applicable. This study used a publicly available, de-identified MRI dataset (Kaggle, Chakrabarty 2019) and did not involve experiments on human or animal subjects.

Informed Consent Statement

Not applicable.

Data Availability Statement

The dataset used in this study is publicly available on Kaggle: <https://www.kaggle.com/datasets/navoneel/brain-mri-images-for-brain-tumor-detection> (accessed 2 July 2025).

Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

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